

Advanced Power Management in a Grid-Connected Solar-Wind Integrated DC Microgrid for Fast Electric Vehicle Charging and AC Load Applications

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To Cite this Article

C. Sai Kumar, M. Lokanadham & Dr. K. Siva Kumar (2025). Advanced Power Management in a Grid-Connected Solar-Wind Integrated DC Microgrid for Fast Electric Vehicle Charging and AC Load Applications. International Journal for Modern Trends in Science and Technology, 11(06), 155-167. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15715144>

Article Info

Received: 30 May 2025; Accepted: 19 June 2025.; Published: 22 June 2025.

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KEYWORDS

DC microgrid,
Solar photovoltaic (PV),
Wind energy,
Fast electric vehicle charging,
AC load support,
Neutral Point Clamped (NPC) converter,
Bidirectional DC-DC buck-boost converter,
Vehicle-to-grid (V2G)

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a grid-connected DC microgrid system integrating solar photovoltaic (PV) and wind energy sources for high-power electric vehicle (EV) charging and AC load support. The system employs a Neutral Point Clamped (NPC) converter to reduce voltage stress on power electronic components, improve power conversion efficiency, and enhance system stability and power quality. To manage the growing energy demand from the rapid adoption of EVs, the proposed architecture includes a bidirectional DC-DC buck-boost converter for efficient EV battery charging and discharging. This converter enables flexible power flow control, allowing both fast charging (80–240 kW within ~30 minutes) and discharging modes, such as vehicle-to-grid (V2G) operation. The system utilizes renewable energy from solar and wind sources to supply the high charging power while mitigating voltage instability and reducing stress on the conventional grid. Additionally, during low charging activity or peak demand periods, surplus renewable energy can be exported to the grid, thereby enhancing grid resilience. The system's performance is evaluated through MATLAB/Simulink simulations, incorporating a coulomb counting-based State of Charge (SOC) estimation method to monitor battery performance. Simulation results confirm improved power quality, reduced grid dependency, and stable operation of the proposed DC microgrid under dynamic load and generation conditions.

I. Introduction

The global transportation sector is undergoing a significant transformation, largely fueled by the increased adoption of electric vehicles. This shift is motivated by rising environmental concerns, depletion of fossil fuels, and strong government policies aimed at reducing carbon emissions [1]. Electric vehicles offer significant advantages such as improved energy efficiency, lower operating costs, and reduced greenhouse gas emissions compared to traditional internal combustion engine vehicles [2][3]. However, the rapid expansion of electric vehicles is posing substantial challenges to the existing power grid infrastructure, particularly due to the increased demand for fast and high-power charging stations [4][5]. Fast charging stations typically require power levels ranging from 80 kilowatts to 240 kilowatts to charge vehicle batteries within a short duration of 30 minutes. This sudden and concentrated power demand leads to issues such as voltage instability, line congestion, transformer stress, and degraded power quality [6][7]. These challenges are exacerbated during peak load conditions or in regions with limited grid capacity. Consequently, it becomes crucial to integrate renewable energy sources into electric vehicle charging systems to supplement grid power and ensure reliability [8][9]. Solar photovoltaic and wind energy systems are among the most promising renewable sources due to their sustainability, abundance, and declining cost of deployment [10]. A hybrid combination of solar and wind power can enhance energy reliability, as the two sources tend to complement each other under varying weather and temporal conditions [11]. Solar energy is more productive during sunny daytime hours, while wind energy is often available during the night or cloudy weather, providing a balanced and continuous energy supply [12][13]. A Direct Current microgrid is particularly well-suited for integrating renewable sources and supporting electric vehicle charging infrastructure. DC microgrids offer reduced conversion losses, simplified control strategies, and compatibility with energy storage systems and DC loads such as electric vehicle batteries [14][15]. Furthermore, they enable more efficient energy management by minimizing the need for multiple AC-DC and DC-AC conversions, which are typically associated with

traditional AC systems [16]. To further enhance power quality and system performance, power electronic converters play a critical role in DC microgrids. In the proposed system, a Neutral Point Clamped converter is used due to its multilevel topology, which helps in reducing voltage stress across semiconductor switches, minimizing switching losses, and improving harmonic performance [17][18]. This makes it particularly suitable for high-power applications such as fast electric vehicle charging and support of AC linear loads. In addition to the NPC converter, a bidirectional DC-DC buck-boost converter is integrated into the system to allow controlled charging and discharging of electric vehicle batteries. This converter facilitates vehicle-to-grid power transfer, allowing the system to support the grid during peak demand or grid instability scenarios [19]. The bidirectional feature enables not only efficient fast charging but also discharging of stored energy back into the grid or to support local AC loads [20]. The system also supports AC linear loads, which adds further flexibility and utility to the microgrid. Since most residential, commercial, and industrial consumers rely on AC power, including AC loads in the DC microgrid architecture necessitates reliable and efficient DC-AC conversion. The presence of both DC and AC loads introduces complexity, but it also increases the applicability of the microgrid in real-world conditions [21]. Effective battery management, particularly accurate estimation of the state of charge, is vital for safe and efficient operation of electric vehicle charging systems. In this work, a coulomb counting method is used for state of charge estimation. This method is based on the integration of current over time and provides a simple yet effective way to monitor battery charge levels in real-time [22]. It ensures optimal battery usage, prevents overcharging, and extends battery life. Coordinating multiple energy sources, energy storage devices, and variable loads within a DC microgrid requires an advanced power management strategy. The proposed system employs a centralized control approach to manage energy flow dynamically, ensure power balance, and maintain voltage and frequency stability [23]. The controller regulates the operation of converters, prioritizes renewable energy utilization, and mitigates power quality issues. To validate the performance of the proposed system, detailed simulations are carried out in

MATLAB/Simulink. The simulation environment models the behavior of the solar photovoltaic and wind energy systems, electric vehicle charging and discharging operations, AC load behavior, and grid interaction under varying operating conditions [24]. The system is tested for different scenarios such as partial shading, wind speed variation, peak EV charging, and grid export operations [25]. Results demonstrate improved system stability, reduced dependency on the grid, enhanced power quality, and effective load sharing among sources.

II. System Configuration

The proposed system is a grid-connected DC microgrid that integrates solar photovoltaic (PV) and wind energy sources to supply fast electric vehicle (EV) charging stations and AC linear loads as shown in Fig.1. The system includes renewable energy interfaces, bidirectional converters, an advanced power conversion stage, and centralized control. The solar PV array is connected to a DC-DC boost converter equipped with an Incremental Conductance (IC) Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) algorithm, improving solar energy extraction efficiency. Wind energy is harvested using a wind turbine coupled with a Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator (PMSG), which is converted to regulated DC power using an active rectifier. The wind energy system employs the Tip Speed Ratio (TSR) MPPT method to achieve maximum power output under fluctuating wind conditions. A Neutral Point Clamped (NPC) multilevel converter interfaces the DC microgrid with the main AC grid and supplies AC linear loads, improving overall system performance. A bidirectional DC-DC buck-boost converter connects the DC bus to the EV battery system, supporting fast charging and vehicle-to-grid (V2G) operation. The system is coordinated through a centralized power management controller that monitors source generation, load demand, and EV battery state of charge, dynamically adjusting converter operation to maintain voltage stability, optimize power flow, and enhance grid resilience.

III. Designing and development of DC microgrid for EVS

A DC microgrid is an advanced energy management system designed for electric vehicle (EV) charging. It

combines renewable energy sources, energy storage, and bidirectional power flow capabilities to optimize charging efficiency and grid interaction. The system uses solar and wind energy as primary sources, with grid support to ensure continuous power availability. The photovoltaic array captures solar energy and employs a P&O maximum power point tracking boost converter for enhanced efficiency. The wind power generation system uses a permanent magnet synchronous generator (PMSG) for variable-frequency AC output, which is converted to DC using a neutral-point clamped (NPC) rectifier for improved efficiency. The integration of solar and wind energy enhances system reliability and reduces dependence on the utility grid. A bidirectional AC-DC voltage source converter manages the grid connection, ensuring high power quality and supporting grid-to-vehicle and vehicle-to-grid operations. The centralized DC bus interconnects all power sources, and a high-power DC-DC converter regulates voltage levels for different charging modes. The charging infrastructure accommodates multiple EVs simultaneously, ensuring fast and effective charging without grid instability. An energy storage system (ESS) stores excess renewable energy and supplies power during low generation periods, promoting sustainability and reducing reliance on the grid.

- Energy Storage Systems (ESS): Batteries to store excess energy.
- Wind Energy System: AC power from wind turbines is converted to DC using a Neutral Point Clamped (NPC) converter and integrated into the DC bus.
- Grid Connection: A bidirectional NPC-based AC-DC voltage source converter (VSC) allows power exchange with the grid, enabling vehicle-to-grid (V2G) and grid-to-vehicle (G2V) operations.
- EV Charging Stations: The DC bus supplies power to multiple EV chargers, which operate in constant voltage or constant current mode for efficient charging.

The power balance equation in the DC microgrid can be expressed as:

$$P_{PV} + P_{wind} + P_{Grid} = P_{Load} + P_{ESS} + P_{ev}$$

Fig. 1. Circuit configuration of the proposed charging station.

A. Solar PV power generation system

a. Solar PV boost converter system configuration

The solar power system in a DC microgrid is crucial for efficient energy conversion and integration with other renewable energy sources. A perturb and observe (P&O) maximum power point tracking (MPPT) boost converter is used to optimize power extraction from the photovoltaic (PV) array, ensuring it operates at its maximum power point under varying solar irradiance conditions as shown in Fig.2. The P&O MPPT algorithm continuously adjusts the operating point by introducing small perturbations to the duty cycle of the DC-DC boost converter. This architecture ensures stable power distribution for EV fast charging stations, minimizing power losses and improving overall efficiency. The DC microgrid benefits from this configuration by achieving improved renewable energy utilization, reduced reliance on grid power, and enhanced power quality. The bidirectional energy flow capability allows for effective integration with battery storage systems, ensuring energy availability even during low solar generation periods. Implementing this solar P&O MPPT boost converter allows the DC microgrid to manage power distribution, support multiple EV chargers, and enhance sustainability by reducing carbon emissions through increased renewable energy penetration.

1. Single-Diode Solar PV Model: Designing a single-diode solar PV model involves analyzing the electrical characteristics of a photovoltaic (PV) cell. The single-diode model is one of the most commonly used to simulate the behavior of a PV cell. This model includes one diode, a current source, and

series and shunt resistances to represent losses as shown in fig.3.

2. Basic Equation of the Single-Diode Model: The equation that governs the behavior of the single-diode PV model is derived from Kirchhoff's current law (KCL):

Fig. 2 solar PV INC MPPT DC-DC boost converter

$$I = I_{ph} - I_D - I_{sh} \quad (1)$$

Where: I = output current of the PV module (A), I_{ph} = photocurrent, the current generated by light (A), I_D = diode current (A), I_{sh} = shunt current (A)

Fig. 3 equivalent model of PV solar.

3. Diode Current (ID): The current through the diode is described by the Shockley diode equation:

$$I_D = I_0 \left(e^{\frac{V+IR_s}{nV_t}} - 1 \right) \quad (2)$$

Where: I_0 = reverse saturation current of the diode (A), V = voltage across the PV cell (V), R_s = series resistance (Ω), n = diode ideality factor (typically between 1 and 2), V_t = thermal voltage (V), given by $V_t = kT/q$

Here:

k = Boltzmann constant (1.38×10^{-23} J/K), T = temperature in Kelvin (K), q = electron charge (1.6×10^{-19} C)

4. Shunt Current (I_{sh}): The current through the shunt resistance R_{sh} is modeled as:

$$I_{sh} = \frac{V+IR_s}{R_{sh}} \quad (3)$$

5. Equation of the Single-Diode PV Model: By substituting the expressions for I_D and I_{sh} into the main current equation, we get the complete form of the single-diode model:

$$I = I_{ph} - I_0 \left(e^{\frac{V+IR_s}{nV_t}} - 1 \right) - \frac{V+IR_s}{R_{sh}} \quad (4)$$

6. Photocurrent I_{ph} : The current generated by the cell due to light is proportional to the incident light and is affected by temperature. It can be modeled as:

$$I_{ph} = [I_{ph,ref} + \mu I_{ph} \cdot (T - T_{ref})] \cdot \frac{G}{G_{ref}} \quad (5)$$

Where: $I_{ph,ref}$ = reference photocurrent at standard test conditions (STC), I_{ph} = temperature coefficient of photocurrent (A/ $^{\circ}$ C), T = cell temperature ($^{\circ}$ C), T_{ref} = reference temperature (usually 25° C), G = irradiance (W/m^2), G_{ref} = reference irradiance at STC ($1000 W/m^2$)

7. Saturation Current I_0 : The reverse saturation current varies exponentially with temperature:

$$I_0 = I_{0,ref} \left(\frac{T}{T_{ref}} \right)^3 e^{\frac{E_g}{nV_t} \left(\frac{1}{T_{ref}} - \frac{1}{T} \right)} \quad (6)$$

Where: $I_{0,ref}$ = reverse saturation current at reference temperature, E_g = bandgap energy of the semiconductor (typically 1.1 eV for silicon)

b. INC MPPT Algorithm – Operating Logic

The Incremental Conductance (INC) method is based on the fact that the derivative of power with respect to voltage is zero at the maximum power point (MPP), positive to the left of MPP, and negative to the right as shown in Fig.4.

$$\frac{dP}{dV} = \frac{d(IV)}{dV} = I + V \frac{dI}{dV} \quad (7)$$

- At MPP: $\frac{dP}{dV} = 0 \Rightarrow \frac{dI}{dV} = -\frac{I}{V}$
- Left of MPP: $\frac{dI}{dV} > -\frac{I}{V} \Rightarrow \frac{dP}{dV} > 0$
- Right of MPP: $\frac{dI}{dV} < -\frac{I}{V} \Rightarrow \frac{dP}{dV} < 0$

Algorithm Steps:

1. Measure $I(k)$ and $V(k)$
2. Compute $\Delta I = I(k) - I(k-1)$, $\Delta V(k) = V(k) - V(k-1)$
3. If $\Delta V = 0$
 - If $\Delta I = 0$: MPP reached \rightarrow No change
 - If $\Delta I > 0$: Left of Mpp \rightarrow Decrease voltage (decrease duty)
 - If $\Delta I < 0$: Right of MPP \rightarrow Increase voltage (increase duty)
4. $\Delta V \neq 0$
 - If $\frac{\Delta I}{\Delta V} = -\frac{I}{V}$: MPP
 - If $\frac{\Delta I}{\Delta V} > -\frac{I}{V}$: Left of Mpp \rightarrow Decrease duty
 - If $\frac{\Delta I}{\Delta V} < -\frac{I}{V}$: Right of MPP \rightarrow Increase duty

Fig. 4. Flow chart of INC algorithm of MPPT for solar conversion.

c. Boost Converter Design

The boost converter steps up the PV voltage to the required DC bus voltage. The output voltage of the boost converter is given by as shown in Fig.5:

Fig.5 DC-DC unidirectional boost converter

$$V_o = \frac{V_{pv}}{1-D} \quad (9)$$

Where: V_o = Output voltage of boost converter (V), V_{pv} = Input PV voltage (V), D = Duty cycle of the converter
The inductor value is selected to ensure continuous conduction mode (CCM) operation:

$$L = \frac{V_{pv}(1-D)}{f_s \cdot \Delta I_L} \quad (10)$$

where: L = Inductor value (H), f_s = Switching frequency (Hz), ΔI_L = Inductor ripple current (A)

The output capacitor is designed to minimize voltage ripples:

$$C = \frac{I_o}{f_s \cdot \Delta V_o} \quad (11)$$

Where: C = Output capacitor (F), I_o = Output current (A), ΔV_o = Allowable voltage ripple (V)

B. Bidirectional Buck-Boost Converter for EV Charging in DC Microgrid

The bidirectional buck-boost converter plays a crucial role in managing energy flow between the battery energy storage system (BESS) and the DC bus in a microgrid. This converter enables both charging and discharging of the battery, ensuring stable power delivery for electric vehicle (EV) charging as shown in Fig.6. In buck mode, the converter steps down the DC bus voltage to charge the battery, while in boost mode, it steps up the battery voltage to supply power to the microgrid or EV load. The control strategy dynamically adjusts the duty cycle to regulate power flow efficiently. The converter also helps stabilize the DC bus voltage, mitigating fluctuations from intermittent renewable energy sources like solar and wind. The energy management strategy ensures optimal charging and discharging cycles, enhancing battery lifespan and overall system efficiency.

1. Buck Mode (Battery Charging)

Output Voltage in Buck Mode:

$$V_b = D \cdot V_{dc} \quad (12)$$

Where: V_b = Battery voltage, V_{dc} = DC bus voltage, D = Duty cycle ($0 < D < 1$)

Inductor Current Ripple in Buck Mode:

$$\Delta I_L = \frac{(1-D)V_{dc}}{L f_s} \quad (13)$$

Where: ΔI_L = Inductor current ripple, L = Inductor value, f_s = Switching frequency

2. Boost Mode (Battery Discharging)

Output Voltage in Boost Mode:

$$V_{dc} = \frac{V_b}{1-D} \quad (14)$$

Inductor Current Ripple in Boost Mode:

$$\Delta I_L = \frac{D V_b}{L f_s} \quad (15)$$

Fig.6 principle operation bidirectional dc-dc buck boost converter

c. Double-Loop Controller for EV Charging System

The control strategy for electric vehicle (EV) charging involves a double-loop control system to ensure efficient, stable, and safe charging. The outer voltage loop maintains a constant DC bus voltage, while the inner current loop regulates the battery charging current as shown in Fig.7. A Proportional-Integral (PI) controller is used in both loops to minimize steady-state error and improve dynamic performance.

Fig. 7 double loop ev charging controller

1. Outer Voltage Loop: DC Bus Voltage Control

The outer voltage loop ensures the DC bus voltage (V_{dc}) remains stable and within the desired range. Since variations in EV charging loads and grid fluctuations affect the DC bus voltage, this loop provides a reference current (I_{ev}^*) for the inner current loop.

Error Signal Calculation:

$$e_v(t) = V_{dc}^* - V_{dc} \quad (16)$$

PI Controller Output (Reference EV Charging Current I_{ev}^*)

$$I_{ev}^*(t) = K_{pv} e_v(t) + k_{iv} \int e_v(t) dt \quad (17)$$

Where: I_{ev}^* = Reference charging current for the inner loop, K_{pv} = Proportional gain of voltage controller, K_{iv} = Integral gain of voltage controller

This reference current is then passed to the inner current loop for precise battery charging control.

2. Inner Current Loop: Battery Current Control

The inner current loop ensures the EV battery is charged with a smooth and regulated current to prevent over current issues and battery degradation. The PI controller in this loop generates the duty cycle for the DC-DC converter (buck or boost).

Error Signal Calculation:

$$e_i(t) = I_{ev}^* - I_{ev} \quad (18)$$

PI Controller Output (Duty Cycle Control)

$$D(t) = K_{pi}e_i(t) + k_{ii} \int e_i(t) dt \quad (19)$$

Where: D = Duty cycle of the DC-DC converter, K_{pi} = Proportional gain of current controller, K_{ii} = Integral gain of current controller

This duty cycle (D) is applied to the DC-DC converter, adjusting the output voltage and current to regulate battery charging.

C. Wind Power Conversion for EV Charging in DC Microgrid

Wind energy conversion in a DC microgrid for electric vehicle (EV) charging involves multiple power conversion stages to ensure stable and efficient power transfer. The wind turbine generates variable-frequency AC power, which is rectified into DC and further regulated to match the microgrid voltage. A Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator (PMSG) is commonly used due to its high efficiency and reliability. The generated AC power is rectified using a three-phase active rectifier, converting it into DC voltage as shown in Fig.8. Since wind speed variations lead to fluctuations in the DC output voltage, a boost converter is employed to regulate and maintain a stable DC voltage suitable for the microgrid. The Neutral-Point Clamped (NPC) converter is used as a bidirectional AC-DC voltage source converter (VSC) for wind integration, ensuring power factor correction (PFC) and bidirectional power flow. The wind energy conversion system (WECS) operates with a Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) algorithm, Tip Speed Ratio (TSR) control, to extract the maximum available power from wind fluctuations. The regulated DC power is then fed into the microgrid, where it supports EV charging either directly or via battery energy storage systems (BESS). In

this setup, battery storage smooths out power variations, enabling continuous EV charging even when wind conditions fluctuate. The coordination between the wind turbine, NPC converter, boost converter, and the microgrid controller ensures stable voltage and efficient energy distribution for EV charging. The wind power system enhances the microgrid's resilience by reducing dependence on the grid and improving renewable energy utilization.

Fig. 8 wind conversion system

1. Wind Power Generation Equation

$$P_w = \frac{1}{2} \rho A C_p v_w^3 \quad (20)$$

Where: P_w = Wind power output (W), ρ = Air density (kg/m³), A = Swept area of the turbine (m²), C_p = Power coefficient (typically 0.3 - 0.5), v_w = Wind speed (m/s)

2. Tip Speed Ratio (TSR) for MPPT Control

$$\lambda = \frac{\omega R}{v_w} \quad (21)$$

Where: λ = Tip speed ratio, ω = Rotor angular velocity (rad/s), R = Blade radius (m)

3. Machine Side Control

The generation of a wind speed reference plays a significant role in the machine side control to extract maximum power from the wind turbine. The control diagram of PMSG connected with active rectifier is shown in Fig. 9. The reference rotor speed is obtained from the optimal tip speed ratio and actual wind speed. The reference speed is:

$$\omega_m^{opt} = \frac{\lambda'_{opt} v_w}{R} \quad (22)$$

where ω_m^{opt} represents reference rotor speed.

The speed error, obtained from the optimal wind speed and actual speed of PMSG, is regulated as reference electromagnetic torque using the PI speed controller, i.e.:

Fig.9 Wind conversion controller

$$\bar{\omega}_r^{error} = \bar{\omega}_m^{opt} - \bar{\omega}_r \quad (23)$$

$$T_e^* = k_{p,s}(\omega_r^{error}) + k_{i,s} \int (\omega_r^{error}) dt \quad (24)$$

where ω_r^{error} represents rotor speed error; T_e^* represents reference electromagnetic torque; $K_{p,s}$ represents pro-portion gain of speed controller; and $K_{i,s}$ represents integral gain of speed controller.

The reference q -axis current is: (i_{qm}^*)

$$i_{qm}^* = \frac{4T_e^*}{3P} \quad (25)$$

The reference voltage is generated using an inner loop current controller to control the machine side converter.

The d - q axis references are:

$$v_{qm}^* = k_{p,mc}(i_{qm}^* - i_{qs}) + k_{i,mc} \int (i_{qm}^* - i_{qs}) dt - \omega_e L_s i_{ds} \quad (26)$$

$$v_{dm}^* = k_{p,mc}(i_{dm}^* - i_{ds}) + k_{i,mc} \int (i_{dm}^* - i_{ds}) dt - \omega_e (L_s i_{ds} + \lambda_m) \quad (27)$$

where V_{dm}^* , V_{qm}^* represent reference machine voltage in d - q axis; represent reference stator current in d - q axis; I_{dm}^* , I_{qm}^* represents proportional gain of machine current controller; and $K_{p,mc}$, $K_{i,mc}$ represents integral gain of machine current controller. The d - q axis machine voltage references are converted into three-phase machine voltage references using inverse park transformation which are fed as in-puts to the pulse width modulation (PWM) generator to generate the switching signal to control the three-phase machine side active rectifier to achieve maximum power from the wind turbine.

Fig. 10 Grid conversion controller

D. Grid-Side Converter Control Using PI Controller

In a DC microgrid, the grid-side converter (GSC) is responsible for bidirectional power exchange between the grid and the DC bus, ensuring power factor correction (PFC) and maintaining stable DC voltage. The neutral-point clamped (NPC) bidirectional AC-DC voltage source converter (VSC) is commonly used for efficient power conversion. The control strategy for the grid-side converter is implemented in the synchronous dq reference frame, where the d-axis controls the DC-link voltage and the q-axis controls the reactive power. A PI controller is used for regulating V_d , V_q , I_d , and I_q to ensure stable and efficient operation. The control structure consists of an outer voltage control loop that regulates the DC-link voltage and an inner current control loop that controls the grid currents. The reference dq currents (I_{dref} and I_{qref}) are derived from the voltage controller, and a PI controller is used to minimize the error between the reference and actual values. The d-axis control ensures that the active power flow is regulated by maintaining the DC-link voltage; while the q-axis control ensures that the reactive power is minimized (or controlled as required) as shown in Fig.10. The voltage and current equations for the grid-side converter are derived from the Park transformation of the three-phase AC system, making it easier to control the power flow efficiently.

1. d-q Axis Voltage Equations

$$V_d = R_s I_d + L_s \frac{dI_d}{dt} - \omega L_s I_q + V_{gd} \quad (28)$$

$$V_q = R_s I_q + L_s \frac{dI_q}{dt} + \omega L_s I_d + V_{gq} \quad (29)$$

3. Active and Reactive Power Equations

$$P = \frac{3}{2} (V_d I_d + V_q I_q) \quad (30)$$

$$Q = \frac{3}{2} (V_q I_d - V_d I_q) \quad (31)$$

Where: P = Active power (W), Q = Reactive power (VAR)

4. PI Controller for d-q Current Control

$$V_d^{ref} = K_p(I_d^{ref} - I_d) + K_i \int (I_d^{ref} - I_d) dt \quad (32)$$

$$V_q^{ref} = K_p(I_q^{ref} - I_q) + K_i \int (I_q^{ref} - I_q) dt \quad (33)$$

Where: K_p, K_i = PI controller gains, V_d^{ref}, V_q^{ref} = Reference d-q axis voltages

The PI controller ensures accurate current regulation by adjusting the error between reference and actual d-q currents. The grid-side converter uses these control strategies to maintain power quality, regulate the DC-link voltage, and manage bidirectional power flow between the grid and the DC microgrid efficiently.

5. PI Controller for DC-Link Voltage Regulation

The DC-link voltage PI controller generates the reference d-axis current:

$$I_d^{ref} = K_{p_{dc}}(V_{dc}^{ref} - V_{dc}) + K_{i_{dc}} \int (V_{dc}^{ref} - V_{dc}) dt \quad (34)$$

Where: I_d^{ref} = Reference d-axis current (A), V_{dc}^{ref} = Reference DC-link voltage (V), V_{dc} = Actual DC-link voltage (V), $K_{p_{dc}}, K_{i_{dc}}$ = PI controller gains for DC voltage regulation

This control strategy ensures that the DC-link voltage remains stable under varying grid conditions, enabling efficient energy exchange between the grid and the DC microgrid.

E. neutral point clamped bidirectional converter design

In an NPC (Neutral-Point-Clamped) converter used in an electric vehicle (EV) charging station, the converter ensures efficient AC-DC and DC-AC conversion while maintaining high power quality. The three-level NPC topology is commonly applied due to its ability to handle higher voltages with reduced Total Harmonic Distortion (THD), making it ideal for charging stations as shown in Fig.11.

Fig.11 schematic diagram of NPC voltage sources converter

1. Phase Voltage Equations (Three-Phase NPC Converter)

The converter generates three levels of output voltage: $+\frac{V_{dc}}{2}$, 0 and $-\frac{V_{dc}}{2}$

For each phase (a, b, and c):

$$V_{an} = \frac{V_{dc}}{2} \cdot s_a \quad (35)$$

$$V_{bn} = \frac{V_{dc}}{2} \cdot s_b \quad (36)$$

$$V_{cn} = \frac{V_{dc}}{2} \cdot s_c \quad (37)$$

Where: V_{an}, V_{bn}, V_{cn} are the phase-to-neutral voltages, s_a, s_b, s_c are the switching functions for each phase and take values of +1, 0, or -1 depending on the switch states, V_{dc} is the DC-link voltage.

2. Neutral Point Voltage Equation

The neutral-point voltage drift is a critical issue in NPC converters. The neutral-point current must be balanced to avoid voltage unbalance in the capacitors. For the neutral-point voltage V_{np} , the following equation holds:

$$V_{np} = \frac{V_{c1} - V_{c2}}{2} \quad (38)$$

$$V_{np} = \frac{V_{c1} - V_{c2}}{2} \quad (39)$$

Where: V_{c1} and V_{c2} are the voltages across the upper and lower capacitors of the DC-link.

3. Neutral-Point Current

The neutral-point current I_{np} is defined as the current flowing through the neutral point and depends on the imbalance in switching.

$$I_{np} = I_{upper} - I_{lower} \quad (40)$$

Where: I_{upper} is the current through the upper switches, I_{lower} is the current through the lower switches.

The neutral-point current must be controlled to ensure that $I_{np} = 0$ to avoid drift in the neutral-point voltage.

4. AC to DC Conversion Equations

For the AC-DC conversion process in the NPC converter, the output DC voltage V_{dc} is related to the input AC voltage V_{in} as follows:

$$V_{dc} = \frac{3\sqrt{2}}{\pi} V_{in} \quad (41)$$

Where: V_{in} is the RMS value of the input AC voltage.

The DC current I_{dc} is related to the AC current I_{in} as:

$$I_{dc} = \frac{3\sqrt{2}}{\pi} I_{in} \quad (42)$$

Where: V_{in} is the RMS value of the input AC voltage.

5. Power Flow Equations

The power delivered from the AC side to the DC side during charging is given by:

$$P_{AC} = 3V_{in}I_{in} \cos(\phi) \quad (43)$$

Where: P_{AC} is the active power transferred from the grid to the EV, V_{in} is the phase voltage, I_{in} is the phase current, $\cos(\phi)$ is the power factor.

The power on the DC side of the converter can be expressed as:

$$P_{DC} = V_{dc}I_{dc} \quad (44)$$

6. Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) Calculation

The NPC converter is designed to reduce THD. The formula to calculate THD in the output current is:

$$THD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} I_n^2}{I_1^2}} \times 100 \quad (45)$$

Where: I_n is the RMS value of the nth harmonic current, I_1 is the RMS value of the fundamental current.

7. DC-Link Capacitor Design Equation

The size of the DC-link capacitor in an NPC converter is crucial for maintaining stable voltage. The required capacitance C_{dc} can be calculated as:

$$C_{dc} = \frac{P_{DC}}{2 \cdot f_{sw} \cdot \Delta V_{dc} \cdot V_{dc}} \quad (46)$$

Where: P_{DC} is the DC power, f_{sw} is the switching frequency, ΔV_{dc} is the allowable ripple in the DC-link voltage.

8. Inductor Design (Ripple Filter)

The inductor value is designed based on the allowed current ripple and switching frequency. The formula is:

$$L = \frac{V_{dc} \cdot D \cdot (1-D)}{f_s \cdot \Delta I_{ripple}} \quad (47)$$

Where: L = Inductor value (in Henrys), V_{dc} = DC bus voltage (in Volts), D = Duty cycle (ratio between 0 and 1), f_s = Switching frequency (in Hertz), ΔI_{ripple} = Allowed peak-to-peak current ripple (in Amperes)

9. Capacitor Design (Ripple Filter)

The capacitor value is chosen based on the desired voltage ripple and the current flowing through the capacitor. The formula is:

$$C = \frac{I_{load}}{4 \cdot f_s \cdot V_{ripple}} \quad (48)$$

Where C = Capacitor value (in Farads), I_{load} = load current (in Amperes), f_s = Switching frequency (in Hertz), V_{ripple} = Allowed peak-to-peak voltage ripple (in Volts).

IV. Simulation Results and Discussion

A. Performance Evaluation of Hybrid Energy-Based EV Charging System

The performance of the proposed hybrid energy-supported system was validated through MATLAB simulation with a total runtime of 1 second. The system integrates solar (40 kW), wind (20 kW), and grid energy sources to support a 25 kW AC load and a 50 kW electric vehicle (EV) charging system. During the initial interval from 0 to 0.2 seconds, there was no power generation from either solar or wind due to the absence of irradiation and wind speed, and consequently, the grid solely powered the system. From 0.2 to 0.3 seconds,

solar irradiance increased from 0 to 500 W/m², resulting in approximately 20 kW of power generation. This trend continued as the irradiance further rose from 500 to 1000 W/m² between 0.3 to 0.4 seconds, allowing the PV system to reach its full capacity of 40 kW. Solar power then remained constant from 0.4 to 1 second at peak generation. Wind power generation commenced at 0.4 seconds, with the wind speed increasing from 0 to 10 m/s, contributing 10 kW of additional power between 0.4 to 0.5 seconds. As the wind speed further rose to 12 m/s from 0.5 to 1 second, the wind system generated its maximum output of 20 kW. With both renewable sources operating at full capacity beyond 0.5 seconds, the grid power consumption significantly decreased. Surplus renewable energy not only met the local load demands but was also exported back to the grid, effectively demonstrating vehicle-to-grid (V2G) and grid-support operations. EV charging activities were dynamically incorporated into the simulation. Between 0.6 to 0.7 seconds, the EV began charging at 6.5 kW, which increased to 12 kW from 0.7 to 0.8 seconds. A V2G operation occurred from 0.8 to 0.9 seconds, where the EV discharged 12 kW back to the grid. Finally, during the interval from 0.9 to 1 second, the EV charging power tapered off, decreasing from 12 kW back to 6.5 kW. Throughout the simulation, the system maintained stability, and the dynamic control approach ensured optimal power flow between sources, loads, and the grid as shown in Fig.12. These results confirm the efficiency of the proposed configuration in adapting to fluctuating renewable energy inputs, supporting both EV charging and AC load demands while contributing to grid stability through intelligent power management.

Fig.12 Simulation Results of Dynamic System Power for Proposed System Working Operation

B. Dynamic Behavior of Renewable Energy Sources in EV Charging

The simulation demonstrates the coordination of a hybrid energy system combining solar, wind, and grid sources to supply AC loads and support electric vehicle charging. Initially, the grid serves as the sole energy provider, maintaining system stability even without load or EV activity. As solar irradiance increases, the photovoltaic system starts generating power, reducing the load on the grid and introducing renewable energy participation. The wind system also begins to generate power as wind speeds increase. The system achieves a balance where AC loads and electric vehicle charging demands are largely supported by solar and wind power. As renewable generation stabilizes, the dependency on grid energy declines and the system exports excess renewable power back to the grid, demonstrating efficient utilization and grid support capability as shown in Fig.13. Electric vehicle charging is introduced dynamically, starting at a lower rate and increasing as more renewable energy becomes available. The system adapts smoothly to changes in environmental conditions and load profiles, maintaining stable operation while optimizing energy flow and minimizing grid stress. This highlights the effectiveness of the proposed configuration in supporting dynamic real-world applications through intelligent energy control.

Fig.13 Simulation Results and Dynamic Power Flow Analysis

V. Conclusion

This paper presented an advanced power management approach for a grid-connected solar-wind integrated DC microgrid designed to support fast electric vehicle (EV) charging and AC load applications. The system effectively harnesses renewable energy using an Incremental Conductance MPPT technique for solar and a Tip Speed Ratio-based MPPT algorithm for wind power, ensuring maximum energy extraction under variable conditions. An active rectifier in the wind conversion stage further enhances power quality and controllability. The use of a Neutral Point Clamped (NPC) converter significantly improves system performance by reducing voltage stress on switching components and enhancing power conversion efficiency, especially in high-power applications. Additionally, the integration of a bidirectional buck-boost converter allows flexible power flow for both fast EV charging and vehicle-to-grid (V2G) energy discharge, contributing to grid support during peak demand or instability. Simulation studies performed in MATLAB/Simulink demonstrate that the proposed system not only ensures stable DC bus voltage and efficient load sharing but also improves power quality and reduces dependency on the conventional grid. The coulomb counting-based State of Charge (SOC) estimation provides reliable monitoring of battery performance during dynamic operations. Overall, the proposed DC microgrid architecture offers a scalable, efficient, and sustainable solution for future EV charging infrastructure integrated with renewable energy and grid support capabilities.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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